

The Enhanced Role of Banks and Financial Institutions Its Impact on the Agricultural Sector

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Abstract

Agriculture is capital intensive since there are many inputs for cultivation. An average rural farmer is always in need of funds for the purchase of seeds, pesticides, hiring farm equipment's and setting up irrigation etc., they then try to get back their investment made on the above input hoping that they would have a good harvest. The farmer allocates the funds received on his harvest for his personal expenses and also tries to save a portion of his funds received from harvest for his future cultivation. The problem which generally arises is that, the farmers on several occasions do not have adequate funds left from their earlier harvest for future cultivation. They hence tend to depend on banks which play a vital role in financing the deficiencies. There could be occasions when the yield is very poor, this leads to excess borrowing by farmers from private lenders at exorbitant rates of interest, hence pulling them deeper under debt.

The banks & other financial institutions play a major role in the life of a farmer when compared to other institutions which could be, Government or Non Govt Agriculture support bodies like ICAR (Indian Council for Agriculture research), NABARD (National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development), ICRISAT (International crop Research Institute for Semi-Arid Tropics) and others, who play an active supporting role in agriculture. However,

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The farmers depend on banks and financial institutions since the interest rates are much lower and they also hope for a loan waivers by the political parties who have promised the same.

The banks and financial institutions take limited role in assisting the farmers. The basic function of banks is to provide financial assistance to the farmers, however most of the farmers have little knowledge of scientific measures to improve the productivity apart from the financial weakness and no guidance in improving farming on latest techniques.

The issue that needs to be addressed for the overall growth of farmers which are currently vital is as follows;

- 1. The high cost of labor*
- 2. The high dependence on power.*

3. *The inadequacy of water for irrigation.*
4. *The ever increasing demand for organic crops.*
5. *Awareness of technologies to improve yield*
6. *The availability of latest technologies for better use of irrigation, man power and other basic inputs including marketing of his produce.*

Since the interest rates are comparatively better and the fact that loan waivers for farmers are generally on top agenda of the political parties in our country. These aspects force the farmers to keep themselves in touch with local bankers.

It is well known that the initiatives taken by the bankers towards helping the famers is far from satisfactory. Even though it is true that Banking is basically meant to provide financial assistance to the farmers. It should also be understood that majority of the farmers who are not prosperous and have suffered problems due to consistent losses are not willing to take the advice offered by others any government or non-governmental agency professionally when compared to Banks or Financial Intuitions.

The Banks on their part should take an active part in understanding the Global innovation in Agricultural practices including irrigation and cropping pattern through their specialized staff and ensure that the same in conveyed in an effective way to an average farmer. This would not only help the farmer to increase his output but also help in getting decent profits and help the banker to reduce the bad loans. The effective system of crop management would make the government ponder on better ways on benefitting the farmer rather than waiving off the loans and make them dependent for the same in future.

The best example would be the technique to grow crops with minimal water from countries like Israel or technique of growing rice from salt water from China. It would be difficult for an average farmer to achieve the same without the support of Banks whom they believe the most. Government departments on their part are doing their best, but without commitment and confidence of the Farmers it is not possible to plan the entire activity and hence farmers are in the same state of financial indebtedness. Hence, banks can play a much better role leading to overall improvement of the agricultural sector in the economy.

The banks good evolve certain standard agricultural practices (here in referred as SAgP) which could be implemented to improve, monitor and take timely action on improving the yield. This SAgP should be formulated by scientist and technocrats coordinating together to decide the system. If the same practices is universally implemented it would strengthened the backbone of Indian economy. Hence it is reiterated again that since Bank have the reach, confidence and ability to disburse credit and would boost the recovery of loans and issue of fresh loans they would be the best mechanism to bring in change in agricultural practices.

Keywords: Banks and financial institutions, farming Strategy, Money Lenders, Risk mitigation & Value chain.

Introduction

Rural development plays an important role in the overall socio-economic development of a country like India, where the majority of the population lives in rural areas. Hence, Agriculture is always regarded as the backbone of the Indian economy. The rural sector affects almost all the economic activities in the country either directly or indirectly, it also provides employment to the large number of the population in our Country. A large part of the revenue of the government is also generated from the rural lending. The farmers in our country are exploited by local money lenders who force them to pay exorbitant rate of interest and many are forced to sell their product at lower price to them. Farmers in rural areas also face the risk of unpredictable yield of their crops due to high dependency on monsoon. Apart from the financial problems, they also suffer from lack of good seeds, high cost of eco- friendly fertilizers, rapidly falling ground water table. Non availability of effective labor and deficiencies of other facilities which leads to poor agricultural output.

Banks and financial institutions: A bank is a financial institution licensed to receive deposits and make loans. Banks may also provide financial services such as wealth management, currency

exchange, and safe deposit locker financial institution (FI) is a company engaged in the business of dealing with financial and monetary transactions such as deposits, loans, investments, and currency exchange.

Farming strategy: the farmers with their experience can be encouraged to implement farming strategy regarding cropping pattern seasonal variations availability of water and empower this knowledge with good co-ordination with the Research centers of Bank or other financial Institutions, thus helping themselves and the loan providers.

Apart from the above, banks can encourage the farmers to attend the training programs conducted for them to adopt better farming practices and to get a better yield.

Value chain: the important things apart from harvesting for the farmers is to secure the crops by proper storage transportation and marketing the products the farmers is generally unaware of the customer requirements and is affordability office products and depends upon middleman to market is goods. The middleman on many occasions are unscrupulous and make big margins hence depriving the farmers the price due on his yield and charging premium rates to customers

Moneylenders: Are those whose primary business is lending money for various purpose like farming marriage function educational activity to the local farmers.

They include landlords agriculture is merchant and charge high rate of interest and threatens the farmers in case if they fails to pay back the loans due to fluctuation in the crop yield and expected Returns.

SAgP: The standard agricultural practices refers to the best use of fertilizers seeds of specific quality which could be based on feedback received from earlier confirmed and successful use of the same, similarly the salinity test of the soil and most suitable cultivation based on scientific methods should be incorporated. Apart from the above the Geographic conditions and climate and the best available alternative options which can be used in cultivation should be updated in the standard agricultural practices. Hence, once the best inputs are incorporated in the standard agricultural practices it could be proposed, documented and monitored for enhancing quality of Agriculture practices .The research bodies Relevant and government bodies banks and other stakeholders could be involved initiating the SAgP.

Purpose

1. To find out if Banks can enhance their roles for agricultural development in rural areas.
2. To understand the barriers which the Banks face for agricultural development in rural areas.
3. To understand the various ways in which farmers could be educated about financing for self-development.
4. To study the risk factors inherent in agriculture which often restricts financial institutions from lending. (The risk factors like insufficient rains, floods pest infestation)

Methodology

The research is focused on the financial and technical assistance that could be provided for a farmer willing to incorporate the latest techniques in framing. This is primarily to increase his profitability and reduction of dependence on vagaries of nature.

It is hereby proposed to conduct a qualitative research with depth interview on the existing agricultural technique adopted by the farmers. The respondent chosen are the few farmers who are willing to divulge their agricultural practices and are also willing to adopt progressive techniques in farming. A total of five farmers from a select area with similar farming techniques is proposed to be chosen for research. The depth interview is supposed to shoot out more questions from the answer given and hence the interviews are unstructured.

Research Gap

Review of Literature

Year	Authors	Title/Journal	Objectives of the Study	Findings
August 2017	Ajit Kumar & Upasana Mohapatra	International Journal of Engineering Sciences & Research Technology ISSN: 2277-9655 Value: 3.00 CPDEN: IJESS7	The history and important role placed by agricultural finance and its impact.	The study points out how Banks have been playing a major role in financing agriculture and with the changing credit patterns, how Banks could be a major hub for training agriculturists to get better credits from Institutions
Year	Authors	Title/Journal	Objectives of the Study	Findings
June 2015	Sharmishta Matkar & Anil Keshav Jadhao	Agriculture Credit in India: Status and Problems Research Front ISSN (Print) 2320– 6446, (Online) 2320– 8341 Impact Factor–1.115, Vol. 3 No. 2	Understanding the Agricultural credit issues and the challenges.	The credit delivery for the small and marginal Agriculturists has been challenging. This paper suggest various innovative technologies by which Banks can ensure better credit participation and repayment practices by the small and marginal Agriculturists.
Apr. 2016	Rajiben Solanki	A Study of Agriculture Finance by Commercial Banks In India: A Case Study of Central Bank of India. ANMR Journal of Research in Com. & Mgmt. Vol. 5, Issue 4 ISSN-2277-1166	The mode of operation of Agricultural finance and the quantum or disbursal based on the changing needs of farmers by commercial banks.	The study talks about the role of bank credit to the agricultural sector and how it has been increasing over the years due to various schemes. But it also states that the recovery strategy of the loans issued is not proper which if stream lined would enable more funds to be infused into the banks for Agricultural development.

Major Findings

1. Modern technology is not always capital intensive in farming sector
2. Initial capital intensive measures can be used for several crop seasons by planning conservation of soil and related processes systematically.
3. Effective use of internet can help a farmer to understand the internationally preferred cropping practices and banks can play a vital role in understanding the same, Creating a SAgP(Standard

Agricultural practices.) And by sharing it with the farmers. This will also ensure that they could be effective in recovering the loans given to farmer and farmers keeping deposits from the surplus funds. Government could step in by supporting banks who engage with farmers in sharing technology and effective cultivation and irrigation techniques by providing them with various incentives or rewards.

4. Banks hence can play a more humane role by reducing the indebtedness of farmers who on some occasion take their life suspecting that they can never pay back the loans. The technology and best practices handed over at SAgP would improve their lifestyle and outlook in the farming sector.
5. Farming is generally a labour intensive and full time job with very little time for thinking about other aspects or developments in farming.
6. The farmer expect the local seed and pesticide dealer for their feedback while purchasing them, whereas on many occasion they are in fact promoting products with the highest margin and do not have any idea about the quality of seeds and effectiveness of the fertilizers.
7. The farmers felt the need for short term finance, generally repayable within 3 months was also needed on some occasions, they felt that there was no such provision in Banks. Similarly, the banks were not financing for all their needs and on many occasions they had to borrow from other sources/.
8. The documentation for the loans are cumbersome and with too many counter guarantee, this gives an edge to Micro finance organization since they believe in funding groups rather than individuals.
9. Some of the Farmers felt that they had received some guidance on the cropping pattern but there was neither follow-up action or feedback being obtained on the same.
10. The farmers felt that they were unaware of the latest developments in the cropping, irrigation and current technologies related to agricultural practices. This was so since they were unaware of the source of such guidance/

Limitations

The research was initially conducted among 5 farmers and later with 25 farmers of Hoskote Taluk, Jadigenahalli post. The research could not be conducted in other areas due to Lack of time non availability of farmers due to their preoccupation in agriculture. The farmers generally are not confident to speak with strangers and those who were interviewed were based on the references given by farmers by us and whom they were also acquainted.

There could be variation in thought process and agricultural practices of the farmers due to the geographical location, type or crop, irrigation facilities, local government support and access to marketing and credit facilities.

Conclusions

It should be known that no economy can really develop to the better standards until they improve their agriculture and Agriculture practices. Due to recent negative climatic changes and shortage of potable water impacting the world, any good practices which is resilient to the above issues would be advantages to an economy. In the SAgP could be implemented and followed. This could lead to overall growth of the economy and would launch India into the super power League. The banks have proved to be the best mode to deliver financial services including credit, they have also gain the popularity over the years among the farmers. Hence an additional developmental activity added to their existing profile would benefit all the stakeholders.

Suggestions

1. To develop a system of applied research at the district level to understand the local cropping patterns.
2. Banks can also work with various international research organizations to identify and implement the best practices adopted universally and try to implement the relevant practices which could be implemented in our country.
3. The government could also include research and implementation of best agricultural practices under the ambit of existing banking regulations.

Annexure - 1**The General Format of Questions Being Asked in the Depth Interview of this Qualitative Research Project.**

1. Name
2. Region : Taluk / post
3. Education levels
4. Main source of Income and Is your family is involved in the same
5. Crops grown
6. Experience in agriculture
7. Inputs for crops
8. financing for the inputs source of inputs
9. Period of return on investment (harvest)
10. How do you maintain the finance
11. Have you taken loans If so Where In case of loans which source do you prefer and why
12. What are the reasons you prefer to go to the same entity for loan
13. Are you getting any guidance from government department If so what are they
14. Are there helping you in your agriculture
15. Where do you get a news of latest Trends in agriculture: Melas, mobile app, farmer, meetings other if any
16. Which organization / who from the above is in touch with you regularly Rate in order of priority
17. whom do you think is most dependable Cooperative societies Banks and financial agencies other farmers/ successful farmers Government organizations / departments International research bodies
18. If banks and financial agencies are among top priority how do you think ok they can help you in better way further.

Annexure: II**Government Bodies Providing Assistance In Various Facets Of Agriculture**

Agricultural research stations in Kerala
 Indian Council of Agricultural Research
 Central Avian Research Institute
 Central Institute for Cotton Research
 Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants
 Central Research Institute for Dry land Agriculture
 Central Sheep and Wool Research Institute
 Central Soil Salinity Research Institute
 Centre for Sustainable Agriculture

Indian Agricultural Research Institute
Indian Institute of Food Processing Technology
Indian Institute of Horticultural Research
Indian Institute of Natural Resins and Gums
Indian Institute of Plantation Management
Indian Institute of Soil Science
Indian Institute of Spices Research
Indian Institute of Sugarcane Research
International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
KrishiVigyan Kendra Kannur
National Academy of Agricultural Research Management
National Academy of Agricultural Sciences
National Dairy Research Institute
National Sugar Institute
Nimbkar Agricultural Research Institute
Regional Research Station
Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute